

NATIONAL – CULTURAL FEATURES OF SPEECH

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Abstract: The article gives information about comparative study of national-cultural features of speech etiquette in the English and Uzbek languages. The study deals with the similarities and distinctive features of the topic of conversation, addressing, greeting expressions. And it composes accurate and beautiful speech based on the knowledge gained from the theoretical courses of linguistics.

Key words: English and Uzbek languages, speech, speech etiquette, culture, linguistics.

Аннотация: В статье дается информация о сравнительном изучении национально-культурных особенностей речевого этикета в английском и узбекском языках. В исследовании рассматриваются сходства и отличительные черты темы разговора, обращения, приветственных выражений. А также составляется точная и красивая речь на основе знаний, полученных из теоретических курсов языкознания.

Ключевые слова: английский и узбекский языки, речь, речевой этикет, культура, лингвистика.

Speech culture is an important sign of the development of the society, which reflects the spirituality of the nation. It is known that one of the main signs of the independence of any state is that it has a state language. The granting of the status of the state year to the Uzbek language and the introduction of the law on the state language laid the foundation for our independence. Speech culture, as a field of cultural speech, linguistics, literary language norms, speech, communicative qualities of speech, speech styles, shortcomings and mistakes that can be encountered in speech, and pronunciation problems.

Academician A. Khojiev in his work "Explanatory Dictionary of Linguistic Terms" defines the term of speech culture as follows: appointment department; normativeness of speech, its compliance with the requirements of the language-speaking community in a given period of historical development: pronunciation, stress, word usage, form formation, word formation and sentence structure to do speech normativeness also includes clarity, clarity, and purity of thought.

Oral speech in the style of speech sometimes has the influence of written forms, which are characteristic of written speech, dialect, vulgarism, and so on.

There are the following functional forms of oral speech:

1. **Views of everyday literary discourse.** This includes the everyday speech of literary speakers.
2. **Lecturers speech.** This includes lectures and presentations by high school and university teachers, lecturers, and scholars.
3. **Radio and television speech (language).** This includes speeches in literary language on radio and television.

4. **Stage speech.** A special type of oral speech is stage speech. In stage speech, there is an aspiration to speak in a language that is common to the audience, while retaining the linguistic features of the work being performed.

In the English and Uzbek languages addressing words are similar in some cases; however, there are several cultural peculiarities that significantly differ from each other. In Uzbek culture, when addressing stranger the words *aka, opa, xola, otaxon, amaki* are commonly used. They call even strangers with family member words such as *otaxon, (father for old men), amaki and aka (uncle, brother for middle-aged men), uka, o'g'lim (brother, son for young men).*

The scientists who introduced the theory of politeness into science are Brown and Levinson. And their theory has not lost its relevance today. English and Uzbek languages are full of polite words and expressions. As in the Uzbek and English language cultures, there are special types of addresses to relatives and friends. Children usually address to their parents as *nanny, granny or grandpa – buvi, papa or granddad - buva, dad-daddy, dada - dadajon, mummy-mom, oyi - oyijon.* Such addressing as husband like *hubby - azizim, sonny-bolajonim, sis-singiljon yoki singilginam,* is also used during conversations.

In Uzbek language we express the plurality with the help of affix " *lar* " which can sometimes be used also to denote respect to a person who is spoken about. For example: 1) *Dadamlar aytdilar* – respect 2) *Malikaxonlar kelishdi* – respect also whole member of the family. As you see, the affix " *lar* " has a lot of meaning in Uzbek language. In the first example, the plural " *lar* " is added to both the possessive and the participial, but the plural is used in the singular meaning, because we express one person in the sentence, you have to keep in mind that you can't have more than one father: *Dadamlar aytdilar – My father said*

In the second sentence, the plural form " *s* " is added to the noun, and the suffix of voice " *ish* " is added to the verb " *kelmoq* ". With the help of name we express whole member of the family.

Malikaxonlar kelishdi. – Malika have come with her family.

We can say that before learning any language, it is necessary to know at least a little about the history and culture of that language. This helps us choose the words and phrases that best fit the situation and makes communication easier. It is essential to note that speech etiquette of different nations depends on their cultural background, life style and world perception. Therefore, speech etiquette in English and Uzbek has its national-cultural peculiarities which are specific and vary in many cases.

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